

Recent insight and perspective of marine-inspired biopolymers for wound healing applications – A review

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ABSTRACT

There is an increasing necessity for advanced, sustainable, and biocompatible materials for wound healing as therapeutic and diagnostic products. Marine environments, characterized by high biodiversity, offer an underutilized source of natural resources with enormous potential for creating novel materials for dressings. This review highlights the revolutionary nature of polymeric biomaterials of marine origin, with a focus on polysaccharides, like alginate, chitosan, and carrageenan; proteins, such as collagen and gelatin. These biopolymers are outstanding in their physicochemical properties, such as biodegradability, bioactivity, and modifiable mechanical strength, which enable their use in wound-healing systems. Besides, these biomaterials may be easily chemically and physically modified, enabling enhanced multifunctionality and integration into complex biomedical environments. Marine-based biopolymers are renewable, abundant, and offer environmentally benign alternatives to synthetic materials, thereby resolving sustainability concerns in large-scale biomedical manufacturing. This report addresses the recent development of maritime-derived polymers and the resulting wound dressings for state-of-the-art wound healing, highlighting significant challenges and future perspectives.

1. Introduction

Skin protects the inner soft organs and keeps them out of the external environment. It is the largest body organ that supports immunological homeostasis, sensory perception, and thermoregulation [1,2]. The skin provides hydration and protection against harmful agents; any damage to the skin may lead to a wound, which is very dangerous to life unless treated appropriately. The healing period determines whether a wound

is acute or chronic [3]. Acute wounds that burst due to bites and surgical operations, among other traumatic experiences, naturally heal on their own without medical intervention. Chronic wounds present due to medical challenges in case of lack of adequate treatment on acute wounds, or the patient already has diabetes and vascular conditions [4, 5]. Poor healing of such injuries leads to chronic inflammation, inhibiting angiogenesis and causing harmful effects. The escalation of chronic wounds poses significant medical problems and an expensive treatment

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burden to the patients and other socio-economic pressures to society [3, 6]. The many stages of wound healing require specialized medical expertise to manage wounds due to complex and sequential wound healing phases [7,8]. Wound management needs to be effective in accelerating wound healing with enhanced antibacterial activities. Wound dressings are critical in clinical care, and medical practitioners use various wound management techniques. Surgical interventions, such as skin grafting and debridement, are limited in their application because they carry significant risks, including excessive bleeding and tissue destruction, and require a long healing period [9,10]. The dressing of wounds protects against infection and facilitates cell reorganization, thereby improving tissue integration in wound bed. Appropriate wound dressings significantly impacts wound-healing process. Primary purpose of customary dressings is to prevent external contamination; however, they do not often maintain the humid environment needed for proper recovery [11,12]. The dry exudate from the wounds makes bandages stick to the surface, causing pain and increasing the risk of tissue damage when removed, thereby slowing the healing process. Conventional dressings lack the practical attributes needed to control chronic wounds, such as diabetic ulcers [13].

Thus development of advanced, multifunctional dressings with both protective and regenerative characteristics is essential. Recently, biomaterials derived from biopolymers have been developed for various biomedical applications. These consist of wound healing, medication delivery, skin regeneration, bone regeneration, and cartilage repair [14]. Famous polysaccharides have been used for biomedical applications, and they include arabinosyran, chitosan, guar gum, beta-glucan, cellulose, carrageenan, alginate, pectin, and xyloglucan [15]. Likewise, proteins including gelatin, collagen, elastin, and silk fibroin have become increasingly prominent for biomedical applications [15]. The compelling interest in the development of functional dressings stems from the utilization of polysaccharides and proteins as primary constituents for creating innovative wound-dressing materials. These are semipermeable membranes, microneedles, hydrogel, nanofibers, foams, scaffolds, and hydrocolloids [16]. They have been implemented to improve healing effectiveness and have garnered considerable attention for their distinctive characteristics that facilitate the wound-healing process. Biopolymers exhibit multifunctional physicochemical characteristics that are fundamental for applications in the medical sciences, cosmetics, biomedicine, and healthcare [17]. Biopolymers exhibit better biofunctionalities, including biodegradability, biocompatibility, antimicrobial characteristics, cytocompatibility, and improved cell growth and development. The ongoing study aims to address the enduring production issues that limit the mass-production capacity of these materials. High-level nanomedicine studies will require a deep understanding of biology, particularly regarding nanoparticle-tissue interactions, to develop drugs with increased absorption and distribution, thereby minimizing side effects [18].

The marine ecosystem offers enormous resources for the production of biopolymers with high biotechnological significance; however, these remain vastly underutilized due to its immense biodiversity [19]. Sponges in the marine environment exhibit medicinal properties, including anti-inflammatory effects, as well as anticancer, antibiotic, and antiviral effects. It exhibits structural and architectural features, including its porous structure, which demonstrates promise for biomedical applications [20]. Biopolymers have demonstrated superior biofunctionalities, including high biodegradability, biocompatibility, antibacterial properties, and cell adhesion, as well as supporting high cellular growth and development. The existing study aims to address long-term production issues that limit the mass production of these materials. The development of nanomedicine requires a profound understanding of biological systems and, more specifically, nanoparticle-tissue interactions to design medicines with improved absorption and distribution, thereby minimizing adverse side effects [21]. These biomacromolecules possess characteristic physicochemical, biological, and structural properties. Mycosporines, as secondary

metabolites, have potential as functional biomimetic materials that can be utilized, together with bioinspired micro- and nanostructures, to resolve medical problems. Marine biopolymers possess potentials for wound repair and regeneration with enhances, including biodegradability, biocompatibility, and low antigenicity [22,23].

This comprehensive literature review is a synthesis of existing advancements in dressings and the generation of biopolymers of marine origin for wound treatment (Fig. 1). Although many review articles on biopolymers exist, few focus on recent developments in marine-based biopolymers. Consequently, we are addressing gap by providing a contemporary assessment of literature during past 03-05 years regarding progress of biopolymers in wound healing. We start with a general description of wound categories and the types of biopolymer-based dressings used for wound healing, including polysaccharides, proteins, and their sources. Secondly, we captured several important biomedical properties, including physicochemical and biological properties of antibacterial, anticancer, and biocompatible materials, as well as various dressing materials with specialized properties and functions that facilitate wound healing. We examine challenges faced in healing process and define current advancements in dressings employed in diverse wound therapies. This review concludes by applying dressings in wound healing to enhance their efficacy in fostering healing. We highlight the existing barriers and future opportunities of advancing marine-derived dressing materials to improve their application to wound healing.

2. Wound healing applications

Marine-derived polymeric materials have extensive uses in wound healing because of their versatility, sustainability, and adaptability in many medical technologies, as detailed in Table 1. Biomaterials sourced from marine origins, including collagen, chitosan, and alginate, are progressively employed in tissue engineering, drug delivery, and wound healing. Their capacity to facilitate cell proliferation and tissue regeneration renders them very advantageous for scaffold construction. Ongoing research investigates their potential to improve therapeutic outcomes in various medical applications [29]. Marine-origin polymers, touted for their antibacterial and biocompatible properties, are increasingly used in wound dressings to facilitate healing. The compounds help heal tissue by maintaining a humid environment, preventing infection, and accelerating healing. Hydrogel dressings made of chitosan and algae-based dressings that are made of alginate are commonly used in wound healing. It enhances the antibacterial and anti-inflammatory effects, which are further increased by the presence of essential oils, including lavender, which helps the healing process [30]. The different wound healing phases have been illustrated in Fig. 1.

2.1. Normal wound healing

Hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and remodeling of extracellular matrix (ECM) constitute a complicated sequence of events integral to standard wound healing and are crucial for tissue restoration [31]. Nanoparticles have transformed wound healing by facilitating precise distribution of biocompatible chemicals, enhancing mechanical strength, and minimizing toxicity in tailored wound dressings [32]. Novel hydrogels, such as the dual-bionic C-CTS/SA-Ag-dECM hydrogel inspired by mussel and barnacle proteins, demonstrate superior hemostatic and anti-bacterial properties, promoting rapid wound closure and scar-free healing [33]. Additionally, macrophage polarization, facilitated by M2-Exosome-loaded polyethylene glycol (PEG) hydrogels, can enhance tissue homeostasis and accelerate wound healing. Excessive inflammation and the creation of neutrophil extracellular traps can impede recovery, underscoring the necessity for additional research to improve therapeutic options [34].

Fig. 1. Illustration of marine sources, marine-derived biopolymers, and various wound dressing materials to treat different injuries, with emphasis on the different wound healing phases.

Table 1
The different wound types and their treatment using biopolymeric wound dressings.

Wound type	Biopolymers	Dress materials	Biological properties	References
Normal wound	Hyaluronic acid	Hydrogel	Cytocompatibility Granulation Re-epithelialization Collagen deposition Neovascularization	[24]
Diabetic wound	Chitosan	Hydrogel	Anti-bacterial Angiogenesis Granulation Tissue regeneration Collagen deposition	[25]
Chronic wound	Alginate	Nanofiber	Angiogenesis Inflammation Angiogenesis Anti-oxidant	[26]
Cancerous wound	Gelatin	Hydrogel	ROS scavenging Microenvironment	[27]
Pressure ulcer	Carrageenan Sodium alginate	Nanofibers	Biodegradability Biocompatibility Anti-inflammatory	[28]

2.2. Diabetic wound healing

Diabetic wounds provide significant clinical challenges due to impaired healing, increased infection risk, and the possibility of amputations. Adipose-derived stem cells have potential for tissue healing; however, their efficacy is limited by the survival of transplanted cells. Elastin-like polypeptides are biomaterials that enhance the activity of adipose-derived stem cells and mediate angiogenesis [35]. Advanced techniques that aid in wound healing are nanoparticles, hydrogels, photothermal therapy, and 3D printing, which relieve oxidative stress and regulate the microenvironment [36]. Hyaluronic acid-based bio-hybrid microspheres with glutathione improve the vascularization and tissue healing. Marine-derived biomaterials, like scallop byssal protein coatings and algae-based hydrogels, exhibit potential for innovative therapeutic applications in the management of diabetic wounds [37].

2.3. Chronic wound healing

Chronic wounds present a substantial healthcare challenge due to their extended healing duration, primarily resulting from conditions such as ischemia, diabetic foot ulcers, pressure ulcers, and venous ulcers. Electrospun fibers from polymeric wound dressings (nano- and micro-scale) are advantageous due to their biodegradability and cytocompatibility, together with their capacity to carry antimicrobial agents, rendering them effective in the management of chronic wounds [38].

Advanced polymeric materials such as alginate, chitosan, hyaluronic acid, collagen, polyurethane, and silk exhibit bioactivity, facilitate tissue regeneration, and expedite healing. Marine polysaccharides (MPs), like alginate and hyaluronic acid (HA), demonstrate distinctive biological features that influence inflammation and promote wound healing in chronic diseases. However, HA's rapid degradation necessitates chemical modifications to enhance stability [39]. Marine Col, a biocompatible and biodegradable alternative to synthetic Col, has gained attention for its ability to promote cell migration and skin regeneration, particularly in chronic wounds [40]. Nanotechnology (including electrospun nanofibers and metallic nanoparticles) has shown potential for recreating natural tissue structures, enhancing cell adhesion, and preventing infections. Nonetheless, obstacles like as toxicity, expense, and the requirement for extensive production impede clinical translation. Current development of nanobiotechnology and polysaccharide-based wound dressings is essential for improving chronic wound healing [41].

2.4. Cancerous wound healing

Bioactive substances with great potential for cancer treatment can be found in large quantities in the marine environment. Recent advancements in marine-inspired polymeric materials have led to develop innovative drug delivery systems, including a self-heating microneedle patch for skin cancer treatment. 5-fluorouracil and thymoquinone is effectively administered to the tumor site for prolonged tumor suppression using this patch, which incorporates a degraded for sustained release and a dissolvable base for fast release [42]. Natural polysaccharide chitosan is promising for anticancer applications due to its ability to deliver drug at wound site. It applied to enhance drug release efficiency and tumor targeting of polymeric nanoparticles and theranostic systems, including chitosan-grafted graphene oxide hybrid nanosystems [43]. Silver nanoparticles have arose a potent anticancer agents, exerting cytotoxic effects on various cancer cells by inducing apoptosis, activating autophagy, and arresting the cell cycle. AgNPs have been incorporated into hybrid drug delivery systems to enhance therapeutic efficacy [44]. Nanocarrier-mediated drug delivery, encompassing PEGylated chitosan nanoparticles and polymethyl methacrylate hydrogels, has transformed cancer treatment through targeted delivery and improved bioavailability. Functionalized nanoparticles have been employed in colon cancer treatment alongside photothermal therapy utilizing PDA nanoparticles, showcasing the possibility for localized, on-demand medication release [45]. Examples of bioactive marine-derived molecules that have shown anticancer effects through immunological regulation and apoptosis include collagen peptides, omega-3 fatty acids, and cyanobacterial secondary metabolites [46]. Marine-derived biomaterials, including 3D-printed antimicrobial scaffolds, have been investigated for biomedical applications like wound healing and tissue engineering. Selenium nanoparticles have demonstrated enhanced anti-cancer effects and reduced toxicity in scaffolds. These discoveries highlight the promise of biomaterials and nanotechnologies sourced from marine resources for cancer therapy, particularly in enhancing medicinal efficacy, reducing adverse effects, and increasing treatment specificity [47].

2.5. Pressure ulcers healing

The complex biology and persistence of pressure sores and foot ulcers, especially diabetic foot ulcers, present considerable therapeutic problems. The causes of DFUs are diabetic neuropathy, vascular insufficiency, and bacterial infections, and they hinder wound healing. The use of advanced therapies is necessary because conventional treatments, such as insulin therapy, surgical debridement, antibiotic therapy, and conventional dressings, often do not provide optimal healing conditions [48]. Hydrogels are now promising replacements that can mimic the ECM, facilitate cell growth, and support autolytic debridement owing to their three-dimensional (3D) networks, permeability, and hydration

retention. Moreover, Col-based dressings are immune promoters, angiogenic, and tissue regenerative, particularly marine and recombinant-based ones [49]. Novel strategies, such as nanozymes and cold atmospheric plasma (CAP) therapy, have attracted interest for their ability to modulate wound microenvironments, reduce inflammation, and exhibit antimicrobial properties. Furthermore, carboxymethyl cellulose-based scaffolds and alginate-mangosteen combinations exhibit promising bioactivity for wound healing applications [50].

3. Marine-based biopolymers

Marine creatures provide a diverse array of biopolymers, such as polysaccharides and proteins, regarded to have durability, biodegradability, and occurrence. The shift toward bio-based polymers addresses the environmental challenges posed by petroleum-based plastics, which persist for decades and contribute to pollution [51]. Biogenic and plant-based feedstocks are being utilized to produce sustainable polymers with performance comparable to conventional plastics, with a focus on heteroatom-rich compounds, such as those containing C-O and C-N bonds [52]. Advances in polymer science have expanded the use of biodegradable materials across sectors such as agriculture, biomedical applications, and packaging, thanks to their renewability, non-toxicity, and superior mechanical properties [53]. Biopolymers like polylactic acid and polyhydroxyalkanoates serve as viable alternatives in food packaging, delivering robust barrier qualities and antibacterial advantages via bio-based reinforcements, such as essential oils, thus enhancing shelf life and sustainability [53]. Alginate composite materials have been extensively researched and utilized as wound dressings because their excellent durability. They can form hydrogel-like structures that provide a perfect healing environment and exhibit high moisture retention. The biocompatibility, biodegradability, hemostatic, and antibacterial properties of chitosan make it a versatile wound-care agent. Chitosan is suitable for all wound types because its cationic characteristics, which stimulate cell adhesion, accelerate tissue regeneration, and reduce inflammation [54,55]. Nanoparticles, pharmaceutical biomolecules, and other polymers, both natural and synthetic, were combined with the biopolymers. It can surmount its intrinsic deficiencies, including insufficient mechanical strength and inadequate antimicrobial efficacy. These composite solutions enhance properties such as sustained release of pharmaceutical agents, controlled exudate uptake, antibacterial activity, and mechanical strength. Thin films, hydrogels, nanofibers, and biopolymers-based sponges are designed to treat acute and chronic wounds. It emphasizes their capacity to improve patient outcomes, diminish infections, and expedite wound repair and regeneration [54]. Fig. 2 illustrates various marine sources of polysaccharides and proteins.

3.1. Polysaccharides

Recent studies have highlighted the growing interest in marine-derived polysaccharides, such as fucoidans, glucans, mannoproteins, pectic polysaccharides, and alginates, due to their potent antioxidant and antibacterial properties [56]. Factors such as molecular weight, solubility, and functional group composition influence bioactivity. Considering the need for chemical alterations to enhance their biological efficacy. These polysaccharides have demonstrated utility in the food and pharmaceutical industries, particularly in regulating gut microbiota and stabilizing bioactive compounds [57]. Furthermore, plant-derived polysaccharides exhibit significant antibacterial activity by altering membrane permeability and inhibiting nutrient transport. Their structural diversity enables various therapeutic applications, including immunomodulation and anti-inflammatory effects. Despite challenges in large-scale production, the multifunctional properties of marine polysaccharides position them as promising biomaterials for biomedical advancements [58].

Fig. 2. Marine-Inspired Polymeric Materials: A circular diagram displaying polymers extracted from marine organisms, highlighting their origins and potential applications. Key examples include chitosan and chitin from crustaceans, alginate and carrageenan from seaweed, collagen and gelatin from aquatic animals, hyaluronic acid from sharks, and mucin from gastropods. The figure highlights the versatility of these materials for use in biotechnology, healthcare, and environmental solutions.

3.1.1. Chitosan

Chitosan is a biocompatible and biodegradable polymer produced from chitin. It has garnered considerable interest as it is varied applications in biological and industrial sectors. Chitosan, present in crustacean exoskeletons, insect cuticles, and fungal cell walls, exhibits features determined by its molecular weight and degree of deacetylation. Chemical and biological changes, but its limited solubility in neutral and basic environments. Processes such as esterification, acylation, and enzymatic grafting augment its bioavailability and functional flexibility [59]. Chitosan-based dressing materials exist in multiple forms. Nanoparticles, nanofibers, membranes, and hydrogels are extensively employed in drug delivery, tissue engineering, and the food business. Moreover, its reactive amino and hydroxyl groups promote hydrogel formation, enhancing possibilities in medicines and nutrient delivery. Notwithstanding problems including low solubility and restricted mechanical strength, persistent innovations are enhancing its potential in biological and industrial domains [60]. Junpeng Zhou et al. have hydrogels from chitosan for enhanced wound healing applications. Cellular analysis exhibited that hydrogels are biocompatible and boost osteoblastic differentiation. They had significantly higher wound contraction ($95.75 \pm 2.28\%$) than the individual polymeric components and the control groups. Biochemical analysis demonstrated increased hydroxyproline (48.82 ± 1.25 mg/g) and total protein (75.25 ± 1.56 mg/g) in the newly formed granulation tissue, indicating increased collagen deposition [61].

3.1.2. Alginate

Alginate is a naturally occurring polymer obtained from brown

seaweed and certain bacteria. They demonstrate exceptional gel-forming capability, biocompatibility, and biodegradability, rendering them very appropriate for biomedical applications [62]. Despite its inherent limitations in load-bearing tissue engineering due to its soft gel nature, blending with synthetic or natural polymers enhances its mechanical strength, bioactivity, and cell affinity [63]. Alginate-derived hydrogels, fibers, and three-dimensional printed matrices exhibit promise in wound healing, pharmaceutical delivery, and tissue repair. Advanced extraction and bio-refinery approaches are crucial for enhancing efficiency, improving sustainability, and maximizing resource utilization. Notably, sodium alginate hydrogels have exhibited greater than 90% scavenging activity and 93% wound contraction in vivo, underscoring their therapeutic relevance [64]. Xuxiu Lu et al. have created hydrogels from alginate derived from *Sargassum* seaweed to improve healing by regulating oxidative stress and promoting granulation. Hydrogels exhibited a beneficial effect against oxidative stress-induced cellular dysfunction through the activation of the Nrf2 regulatory system. Sodium alginate-derived hydrogels improved endothelial cell mobility and tubular structure development in HUVECs, corresponding with elevated VEGF expression. Angiogenesis, oxidative stress, and diabetes-related pathological abnormalities improved with 200 mg/kg hydrogel intravenously. These effects collectively facilitated accelerated wound closure, highlighting the therapeutic efficacy of these hydrogels as feasible treatment choices for diabetic skin ulcers [65].

3.1.3. Carrageenan

Carrageenan-based biomaterials are attractive because to their versatility, biodegradability, and therapeutic capabilities, such as

antibacterial, antiviral, anticoagulant, anti-oxidant, and immunomodulatory activities [66]. Their solubility in water promotes wound healing by retaining moisture, absorbing exudates, and inhibiting adherence to the wound bed, all while reducing cytotoxicity and discomfort. Carrageenan-based hydrogels, aerogels, and nanoparticles have been explored for nutraceutical and drug delivery, with future research focusing on in vivo trials and environmentally responsive systems [67]. Tissue engineering applications benefit from chemical changes and nanoparticle integration increasing strength in mechanics and controlled degradation. K-carrageenan, when combined with Na-alginate and cross-linked with potassium ions, demonstrates superior wound-healing efficacy. The incorporation of antibacterial compounds, such as silver nanoparticles, further enhances these properties. Additionally, carrageenan-based transdermal membranes maintain drug stability and demonstrate the potential for anti-inflammatory therapy [68]. Nistha et al. have designed biomimetic functional materials from carrageenan using a green approach, with improved cellular behavior for mucosal tissue and drug-delivery applications. The hydrogels showed high biocompatibility, with $190\% \pm 7.07\%$ vitality in RD cells, indicating increased cellular proliferation and non-toxicity to human cells. The materials exhibited significant antioxidant activity, demonstrating a scavenging efficiency of $52.40\% \pm 1.14\%$ against DPPH radicals. The mucoadhesive properties were confirmed by a release rate of 93 ± 6.11 mN from the gastrointestinal membrane. The Hixson-Crowell model most accurately characterized the drug release kinetics, indicating an erosion-controlled release mechanism. The superior cell viability, absence of hemolysis, and biological characteristics of hydrogels render them a potential platform for intravaginal therapeutic delivery [69].

3.1.4. Hyaluronic acid

Hyaluronic acid is commonly employed in therapeutic delivery and tissue engineering due to its biocompatibility, mucosal adhesion, and capacity for modification [70]. Despite its potential in regenerative medicine, lab synthesis remains costly and complex. Its thermoresponsive hydrogels integrated with kappa-carrageenan exhibited regulated release of meropenem, antibacterial efficiency, and enhanced wound healing. Additionally, HA-integrated peptide/saccharide hydrogels exhibited self-healing properties, enhanced fibroblast biocompatibility, and sustained curcumin release for treatment of diabetic wounds. Recent research trying to optimize synthesis, intracellular behavior, and regulatory considerations to improve the clinical applications of HA [71]. Xiangchen et al. have developed hydrogels comprising hyaluronic acid, carboxymethyl chitosan, and puerarin to accelerate diabetic wound healing. They have demonstrated exceptional ability in effluent retention, mechanical flexibility, hemostatic properties, and antibacterial effectiveness. The hydrolysis of amide bonds generated a low-pH bioenvironment in wounds. Hydrogel wound dressings with microalgae created oxygen for 24 h, improving skin oxygenation. Prodrugs like hyaluronic acid and puerarin from the hydrogel showed regulated release and quick, increased wound site drug accumulation. Enhanced angiogenesis and anti-inflammatory actions accelerate wound healing and using microalgae, hyaluronic acid, and puerarin, hydrogel treats type-1 diabetic rats. These factors jointly enhanced the rate of wound healing and improved recovery efficiency [72].

3.2. Proteins

Marine-derived proteins like collagen and gelatin are potential biomaterials due to their biocompatibility, biodegradability, and cell adhesion and proliferation. These proteins' structural closeness to ECM makes them important in tissue engineering, wound healing, and regenerative medicine [73]. Their bioactivity and variable mechanical strength make them ideal for innovative biomaterials. Research is enhancing extraction, modification, and cross-linking methods for therapeutic applications to improve stability and mechanical qualities

[74].

3.2.1. Collagen

Marine collagen, obtained from marine sources, is cheaper, less immunogenic, and diseases less likely to spread. It is extensively utilized in biomedical applications, including drug delivery systems, wound dressings, and scaffolds for tissue engineering [73]. Marine collagen type I increases collagen production and osteogenesis, making it suitable for bone tissue engineering and 3D bioprinting. Collagen from the marine demosponge *Chondrosia reniformis* can prevent bacterial invasion in skin regenerative medicine. Seasonal variations in the molecular properties of collagen may influence the stiffness of biomaterials, and halal concerns regarding marine-derived sources require careful attention in biomedical contexts [75]. Tayyeb Ghadimi et al. have developed a collagen-based sponge blended with Sargassum glaucescens Extract for improved wound healing. Physicochemical and physiological characterization of produced collagen (40 mg/ml)/SGE (1–3 mg/ml) was conducted. The bioactive component of SGE, collagen type (type I, $\alpha 1$, and $\alpha 2$), effective incorporation into Col/SGE scaffolds, thermal durability, and significant hydrophilic properties and absorbing water were all discovered by physicochemical research. Biological investigations showed that SGE exhibits antioxidant, antibacterial, structural stability, and cell-proliferation-enhancing properties without toxicity. Antibacterial and cell viability assessments indicated that the Col/SGE-3 mg/mL sample exhibited the highest cellular activity. Col/SGE in vivo on rat burn wounds enhanced re-epithelialization, dermal remodeling, inflammatory cell decrease, fibroblast proliferation, and collagen accumulation. Thus, the collagen/SGE scaffold demonstrates physical stability and potentially fosters cell proliferation without toxicity, suggesting it may substantially improve wound healing [76].

3.2.2. Gelatin

Gelatin, a denatured collagen, is a popular marine-derived biomaterial for tissue engineering and medication administration due to its gelling and biocompatibility. It is frequently used in the creation of hydrogels and scaffolds, where cross-linking with substances like iron can improve its structural stability [77]. Studies suggest that cross-linking improves gelatin hydrogel performance in biomedical applications by affecting their viscoelasticity. Gelatin is useful for regenerative medicine biomaterials due to its characteristics [78]. Alves et al. produced collagen and gelatin polymeric materials to evaluate the immunologic response for tissue-engineering applications. C57BL/6 mice were injected peritoneally to measure the host's response. The least immunogenic substance, shark collagen, induces low pro-inflammatory cytokines and inducible nitric oxide synthase and high Arginase 1. Shark gelatin expressed more pro-inflammatory markers, but also IL-10 and Arginase. These materials temporarily recruited neutrophils in the mice's peritoneal cavity, but they were almost gone after 24 h. These collagenous materials may activate M2-like macrophages, making them promising biomaterials for regenerative therapy. It contributes to tissue remodeling by inhibiting inflammatory processes [79].

3.2.3. Elastin

Elastin, a key component of dermal extracellular matrix, helps skin elasticity, durability, and wound healing. Its degradation, influenced by aging and environmental factors, leads to structural impairments that hinder proper tissue regeneration [80]. Insufficient collagen and elastin fibers remodel the ECM during wound healing, causing stiff scars and decreased suppleness. Recently developed elastin-based biomaterials improve skin regeneration by recruiting immune cells, modulating inflammation, and increasing angiogenesis [81]. Alginate-based composite films and human elastin-like polypeptides can also influence medication distribution and antioxidant activity. Enhanced wound healing with silk elastin sponges and bovine elastin/tannic acid conjugates reinforces elastin's biological importance [82].

3.2.4. Polypeptide

Polypeptides have emerged equally encouraging agents for wound repair, specifically in enhancing collagen stability and expediting tissue regeneration. Human-like collagen (hCol) fusion proteins, such as hCol-ELP, demonstrate superior stability and enhanced healing properties by promoting epithelial cell proliferation, reducing inflammation, and improving collagen deposition and reorganization, thereby facilitating scar-free healing [83]. Marine-derived polypeptides, including those derived from cold atmospheric plasmas and APs, exhibit multifunctional activities, including free radical scavenging, procoagulant effects, and enhanced revascularization and fibroblast proliferation, contributing to accelerated epithelialization and scarless wound healing. Furthermore, hydrogel formulations infused with marine collagen peptides, such as chitosan/polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) blends, exhibit excellent antimicrobial, hemostatic, and cytocompatible properties, offering the potential for practical wound-dressing applications [84].

3.3. Sources of marine-derived biopolymers

Marine animals, such as seaweeds, crustaceans, fish, marine sponges, and microbes, offer distinct structural and biological characteristics that underpin biopolymers of marine origin used in wound healing. Chitosan is predominantly sourced from the exoskeletons of marine life, like crabs, whereas brown algae serve as a crucial supply of polysaccharides, especially alginates. Ulan is a bioactive polymer produced by green algae. Fish skin and scales contain collagen and gelatin that facilitate haemostasis, cell growth, and re-epithelialization because these compounds are biocompatible, retain moisture, and have inherent bioactivity. Extracellular polymers generated by marine microorganisms, including microbes, mushrooms, and microalgae, exhibit resistance to elevated salinity, pressure, and temperature [85]. These encompass polyhydroxyalkanoates, exopolysaccharides, and sulfated polysaccharides, which demonstrate a diverse array of biological functionality. The capacity to manage and scale production and produce a consistent biopolymer makes marine microorganisms suitable for clinical activities. Marine-derived biopolymers provide sustainable, industrial-scale synthesis by genetically modifying marine animals,

enhancing productivity, purity, and structural homogeneity. Genetic modification improved the production of polysaccharides, and the biosynthesis of collagen and gelatin found in fish can be collected and standardised through aquaculture techniques. It solves problems related to batch-to-batch variability, contamination, and environmental impact, thereby enhancing the viability of marine biopolymers for clinical applications [86]. All these innovations make marine biotechnology a robust and viable source of improved biomaterials for wound treatment. Biopolymers derived from the sea exhibit high biocompatibility and promote extracellular matrix remodeling. Marine microorganism-derived exopolysaccharides have antioxidant and immunomodulatory effects for wound treatment. Marine biopolymers are renewable, ubiquitous, and eco-friendly, and can be transformed into hydrogels, films, sponges, and nanocomposites for wound care applications [87]. The sources of marine-derived biopolymers have been illustrated in Fig. 3.

3.3.1. Marine macroalgae-derived polysaccharide

Marine macroalgae provide most prolific and substantial producers of marine-derived polysaccharides, typically categorized into three primary groups: brown, red, and green algae. Laminaria, Ascophyllum, and Macrocystis are examples of brown algae that synthesize significant biopolymers, including alginate, fucoidan, and laminaran, which have broad industrial and biomedical applications. Agar and carrageenan are principal derivatives of red algae (Gracilaria and Gelidium) due to their robust gel-forming capabilities and exceptional biocompatibility, rendering them significant in pharma and biomedical fields [88]. Green algae are less exploited but yield ulvan, a sulfated polysaccharide with high potential in regenerative medicine. Chemical design and content of these polysaccharides vary by species, environment, and extraction methods, affecting their physicochemical properties and biological functions. In general, seaweed biopolymers are renewable, biodegradable, and highly biocompatible, making them sustainable and valuable for the creation of advanced biomaterials for wound applications [89]. Sónia et al. have created a bioactive sponge infused with biosynthesized AgNPs for wound healing and the management of high-exudate wounds. Nanoparticles with a hydrodynamic diameter of 46.10 ± 0.22 nm and a

Fig. 3. Numerous sources of marine-derived biopolymers for prospective wound-healing uses.

zeta potential of -18.20 ± 1.02 mV showed stability for 14 days. Freeze-drying produced porous sponges made of *Codium* sp. polysaccharide and silver nanoparticles. The sponges biodegraded and swelled, reducing weight by 80% after 5 days. Moreover, the sponges exhibited biocompatibility with fibroblast cells and effectively inhibited microorganism proliferation. Antibacterial and bioactive sponges with biosynthesized silver nanoparticles could absorb wound exudate, boost cell proliferation, and prevent skin infections. These findings support the biological use of macroalgal-derived products and the production of metallic nanoparticles from macroalgal biomass [90].

3.3.2. Marine invertebrates derived biopolymers

Divagrant Invertebrates Marine invertebrates are a rich source of structural biopolymers with strong biomedical promise, such as sponges, molluscs, echinoderms, and crustaceans. Chitin and its deacetylated derivative, chitosan, are predominantly sourced from the exoskeletons of crustaceans, including shrimp, crabs, and lobsters. Antimicrobial, hemostatic, controlled medication administration, and wound dressing applications are possible with these biopolymers. Marine sponges produce biocompatible collagen-like proteins and glycosaminoglycan analogues that aid cell attachment and tissue repair [91]. Equally, marine collagen, gelatin, and other structural proteins are abundant in molluscs such as cuttlefish and squid, which offer beneficial mechanical strength and biocompatibility. Since they are antibacterial, bioadhesive, and hemostatic, these biopolymers offer numerous therapeutic potential. It is, however, necessary to optimize extraction and processing techniques to ensure uniform quality and functionality, while accounting for species-specific differences in composition and structural features [61]. Junpeng Zhou et al. have developed biofilms from chitosan and collagen biopolymers derived from cephalopod gladius to evaluate their biological properties for wound repair. Biofilm exhibited increased angiogenic capacity, as revealed by the chick embryonic intestinal membrane study. The animal model showed that CChF therapy reduced wound width more than control rats ($22.25 \pm 2.45\%$), followed by collagen film ($63.25 \pm 2.08\%$) and chitosan film ($52.67 \pm 1.58\%$). Rats treated with CChF demonstrated 48.82 ± 1.25 mg/g of hydroxyproline in NFGT and 75.25 ± 1.56 mg/g of total protein. CChF-treated groups had higher hydroxyproline levels, supporting histological findings. These findings suggest that CChF speeds healing by increasing scarring, inflammation, and proliferation [61].

3.3.3. Marine fish and by-products derived biopolymer

Marine fish and their processing by-products, including bones, skin, and scales, represent a highly valuable source of protein-based biopolymers including collagen, gelatin, and elastin. Collagen from cod, salmon, and tilapia is biocompatible and low immunogenic, making it ideal for wound dressings and injectable hydrogels. Fish scales contain collagen, which mimics human skin's extracellular matrix and supports cell adhesion, proliferation, and tissue regeneration, promoting skin wound healing [92]. Additionally, gelatin derived from fish skin demonstrates superior moisture retention and film-forming properties, enhancing its utility in pharmaceutical encapsulation and wound care applications. Fish processing waste valorization reduces pollution and yields bio-based materials, supporting a circular and regenerative bioeconomy [93]. Javier et al. explored topical wound healing with *Rapana venosa*, *Cladophora vagabunda*, and grape pomace extracts and grape pomace extract and *Rapana venosa* treat wounds. Marine collagen, marine gelatin, and collagen hydrolysate from *Rapana venosa* were employed, with mammalian gelatin as the control. The extracts and formulations were characterized physicochemically and assessed for thermal stability via thermogravimetric analysis. All formulations demonstrated favorable thermal stability, free-radical neutralization, cytocompatibility, and tissue regeneration. Incorporating *Rapana venosa* sea snail collagen, gelatin, and collagen hydrolysate into mammalian products is beneficial [94].

3.3.4. Marine crustaceans and shellfish waste-derived biopolymer

The seafood sector produces large quantities of shellfish by-products, which are a promising and commercially viable source of functional marine-derived biopolymers. Chitin and its deacetylated derivative, chitosan, have attracted considerable interest in various scientific fields due to its substantial biological potential. The production of hydrogels, nanoparticles, scaffolds and polymeric composite materials from marine-derived biopolymers have enhanced antibacterial and hemostatic characteristics, which promote wound-healing and controlled delivery of therapeutic a [95]. Besides chitin and chitosan, shellfish shells contain substantial amounts of calcium carbonate and bioactive carotenoids, such as astaxanthin, which can be used to improve the functionality of composite biomaterials by contributing to mechanical strength and other bioactive properties. Although this resource is abundant and sustainable, the physicochemical characteristics and overall quality of shell-derived biopolymers may depend on species, diets, and extraction methods. To overcome these obstacles and enhance reproducibility, purity, and functional activity, more sophisticated green extraction procedures, such as enzymatic, microwave-assisted, and other green methods, are under active development and optimization for large-scale industrial use [96].

3.3.5. Marine tunicate-derived rare biopolymers

Ascidians or tunicates are a separate group of sea filter feeders that render a rare form of cellulose called tunicin. High crystallinity, mechanical strength, and biocompatibility make it ideal for biomedical applications. Nanocellulose from tunicates is attractive for wound dressings, tissue-engineering scaffolds, and biomedical coatings [97]. The primary interest lies in the high surface area, biodegradability, and functionalization capability of nanocellulose, which facilitate the customization of physical and chemical properties to suit specific therapeutic needs. Tunicates also create glycoproteins and sulfated polysaccharides, bioactive substances with powerful anti-inflammatory and antioxidant capabilities that could improve derived biomaterials [98]. Their potential notwithstanding, the collection and processing of tunicates remain problematic due to their complex biological structure and aquatic environment. Nevertheless, the unique structural and metabolic properties of tunicates have enabled the development of high-performance biomaterials with features difficult to obtain from Earth's resources, highlighting the advantages they can offer in next-generation biomedical applications [99].

3.4. Biomedical fundamental properties

The physicochemical and biological properties of marine-inspired polymeric biomaterials primarily determine their effectiveness in biomedical applications. Marine-derived biopolymers' ability to process, stabilize, and interact with biological systems depends on their physicochemical properties. Tensile strength, elasticity, and stiffness are essential for structural applications like tissue-engineering scaffolds. These properties can be enhanced by modifying the polymers through techniques such as crosslinking, polymer blending, and nanoparticle incorporation. Fig. 4 illustrates the physicochemical parameters of the dressing materials.

3.4.1. Physicochemical properties

Marine-derived biopolymers' processing, stability, and interactions with biological systems depend on their physicochemical qualities, which affect their biomedical applications. These biopolymers' ability to support biological processes and integrate into tissues depends on molecular structure, solubility, and degradation rate. The ability for chemical alteration further increases their adaptability, allowing for customization to meet specific biomedical requirements. The characteristics of marine-derived biopolymers render them beneficial for delivering drugs and tissue engineering [100]. Catalina et al. have developed a wound-healing system and studied its physicochemical

Fig. 4. Physicochemical and biological properties of marine-derived biopolymers.

characteristics from a marine biopolymer. The use of locally grown marine algae and the transformation of waste into valuable end products for dermatocosmetics and medicinal applications. The produced hydrogels exhibited significant swelling capacity and antioxidant activity. The selected optimal formulation demonstrated enhanced wound closure rates in vitro, suggesting its potential for wound-healing applications [101].

3.4.2. Mechanical properties

Mechanical properties, such as tensile strength, elasticity, and stiffness, are essential for marine-inspired biomaterials, particularly in applications that require structural support, such as tissue-engineering scaffolds. The mechanical performance of these biomaterials can be finetuned through various strategies, including cross-linking, blending with other polymers, and incorporating nanoparticles. For example, the mechanical properties of collagen-alginate films can be adjusted by varying the polymer ratio and the concentration of cross-linking agents, enabling greater control over the material's strength and flexibility for specific biomedical applications [94]. Alessandro Coppola et al. have developed scaffolds from chitosan and collagen for skin tissue engineering. Collagen-chitosan hybrid scaffolds were used in skin tissue engineering to address collagen's mechanical fragility. Collagen formed an interconnected, open-pore architecture that promoted cellular infiltration, proliferation, and swelling, facilitating exudate absorption and wound hydration. The chitosan/collagen ratio can be adjusted to withstand wound-healing stressors, control disintegration, enhance antioxidant properties, and maintain mechanical strength. All scaffold formulas significantly inhibited the proliferation of *Staphylococcus aureus* and

methicillin-resistant bacteria by over 3 log reductions ($\geq 99.9\%$) relative to the control. Chitosan/collagen composites for skin repair require collagen, a renewable resource, for structural, physicochemical, biological, and antimicrobial properties [102].

3.4.3. Wetting properties

The hydrophilicity or hydrophobicity of marine-derived biomaterials affects their water and biological fluid interactions. Hydrophilic materials improve cell adhesion and biological environment interaction, which is necessary for tissue regeneration. In contrast, hydrophobic materials are ideal for applications that require controlled drug or other molecule release. Surface modifications can be employed to tailor the wetting properties of these biomaterials, optimizing them for specific biomedical applications [103]. Gabriele Obino et al. have developed nanofibrous materials from sulfated polysaccharides and PCL with improved hemocompatibility and endothelialization for vascular grafting. The effective functionalization of PCL nanofibers has been shown to improve their hydrophilicity significantly. After 4 days, scaffolds had a confluent endothelium monolayer with anticoagulant and antiplatelet aggregation properties. The blue economy promotes using responsibly obtained marine and aquatic polysaccharides to improve vascular graft design. Renewable biological resources and PCL's constraints are addressed in this sustainable technique to improve TEVG's safety, utility, and longevity. This method enhances patient outcomes and preserves marine biodiversity by integrating biomedical advancements with environmental conservation [104].

3.4.4. Biodegradation

Marine polysaccharide biodegradation is complicated by temperature, pH, and microbial activity. Alginate, chitosan, fucoidan, and carrageenan degrade by enzymatic hydrolysis, oxidation, and microbial decomposition, making them suited for biomedical applications, especially wound healing [105]. Their degradation profiles vary with structural composition, extraction methods, and seasonal or species-related differences, which can affect therapeutic efficacy. Marine-derived biodegradable plastics, such as polycaprolactone, have also gained attention for their potential to reduce environmental pollution [106]. Recent investigations have shown that marine-derived proteins, such as violet sea snail proteins, improve PCL biodegradability in marine environments by increasing biochemical oxygen demand and structural breakdown. Further research is needed to completely understand MPs and biopolymer-based materials' biodegradation pathways to improve their biological and environmental sustainability [107].

3.4.5. Swelling

Hydrogel-based materials hold promise for wearable electronics and biomedical applications; however, excessive swelling remains a significant challenge. A nanocomposite hydrogel with acrylic acid and 2-acrylamido-2-methylpropane sulfonic acid in $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ nanoparticle solution improves mechanical properties upon swelling. It is attributed to pH-dependent coordination cross-linking, which strengthens upon immersion in water, enabling effective motion sensing underwater [108]. Similarly, a poly(sulfobetaine methacrylate)-based hydrogel reinforced with tannic acid-modified montmorillonite exhibits superior anti-swelling behavior due to strong electrostatic interactions, thereby maintaining adhesion in aquatic environments [109]. A hydrogel synthesized from *Enteromorpha prolifera* polysaccharides and boric acid-polyacrylamide exhibits self-healing, tissue adhesion, and swelling regulation, effectively accelerating wound healing in vivo [110]. Moreover, marine-derived biomaterials such as alginate and chitosan are extensively studied for their swelling behavior, where covalent cross-linking enhances stability and modulates hydration properties [111]. Research on seawater-induced swelling mechanisms identifies a three-phase process: wetting, rapid swelling, and equilibrium. Polystyrene microspheres contribute to the structural integrity of PS-PEG hydrogels by mitigating excessive expansion. These developments offer potential solutions for overcoming the limitations of hydrogel swelling in biomedical applications [108].

3.4.6. Mechanical strength and adhesion

Mussels, barnacles, and sandcastle worms have developed unique adhesion techniques, inspiring biomimetic adhesive solutions with improved mechanical strength and adherence [112]. Dihydroxyphenylalanine-based adhesives, derived from mussel byssal proteins, exhibit robust cohesion and toughness, while sandcastle glue-inspired polyelectrolyte hydrogels offer high mechanical resilience [113]. Barnacle cement, characterized by its fibrous nanostructures, enhances adhesion efficiency across a diverse range of substrates. However, underwater adhesion faces challenges such as water absorption and osmotic pressure-induced swelling, reducing mechanical strength. Silicone-based fouling-release coatings (FRCs) exhibit antifouling potential but suffer from weak adhesion to the substrate. Modifications, including hydrogen bonding and π - π interactions, have improved mechanical strength [114]. Similarly, PDMS-PU coatings incorporating polyvinylpyrrolidone, a hydrophilic segment, have exhibited superior antifouling performance. Mussel-inspired catechol-containing adhesives and dopamine-functionalized elastomers have demonstrated self-healing and bio-interfacial adhesion properties, thereby advancing biomedical applications. Advances in microstructural hydrogel adhesives have also optimized wet adhesion for bioelectrical applications. These innovations hold significant promise for biomedical and wound-healing applications [34].

3.5. Biological properties

Biomedical applications depend on marine-inspired polymers' biocompatibility, bioactivity, and cell and tissue interactions. These properties determine how effectively the material integrates with the body, supporting tissue repair and regeneration. These materials must interact well with biological systems to be effective in medicinal applications [103]. Fig. 5 encapsulates the biological features of the dressing materials.

3.5.1. Biocompatibility

Biocompatibility is a crucial characteristic of biomaterials, ensuring that they do not induce adverse immune or inflammatory responses when implanted in the body. Marine-derived polymers typically exhibit good biocompatibility, although variations can occur depending on the source, processing methods, and potential impurities. *In vitro* and *in vivo* evaluations are essential to validate the biocompatibility of particular materials. For instance, marine macromolecule-cross-linked bio-composite scaffolds have demonstrated biocompatibility in subcutaneous implantation studies in rats [103,115].

3.5.2. Anti-bacterial activity

Marine biopolymers like chitosan are ideal for infection management since they are antibacterial. Chitosan's capacity to damage bacterial cell walls or membranes is thought to be the source of its antibacterial activity [73]. Essential oils boost marine-derived hydrogels' anti-bacterial action, reducing infections and speeding wound healing [116]. Cátia Correia et al. created bioactive films from fucoidan and chitosan that have enhanced antibacterial and adhesive properties. Catechol groups (FCat) increased fucoidan's adhesiveness in antibacterial adhesive films made with chitosan. FCat inhibited Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, enhanced fucoidan's antibacterial activities, and solvent-cast FCat films after chitosan amalgamation increased mechanical qualities and processability. Fibroblastic cells flourished on these non-cytotoxic coatings that bonded like therapeutic natural adhesives. Researchers found that antibacterial and sticky films can replace cytotoxic synthetic adhesives for soft-tissue repair [117]. Yapeng Lu et al. created a gelatin-fucoidan dressing that speeds wound healing and is antibacterial and anti-inflammatory. Gel&Fuc-TA, a hydrogel wound dressing made of tilapia fish skin gelatin, fucoidan, and tannic acid, was crosslinked using an eco-friendly manner to improve wound healing. Stable network architecture, swelling and releasing properties, antibacterial, antioxidant, hemostatic, and cytocompatible features characterize the hydrogel. Tissue regeneration and angiogenesis are promoted by increased VEGF, CD31, and α -SMA expression, collagen deposition, wound microbiota changes, and inhibition of LPS, TLR2, and TLR4-associated inflammation. Moreover, Gel&Fuc-TA promotes M2 macrophage polarization, reduces pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-6, IL-1 β , TNF- α), and boosts anti-inflammatory and pro-healing factors (Arg-1, IL-10, TGF- β), accelerating wound healing [118].

3.5.3. Anti-cancer

Marine-derived pharmaceuticals continue to revolutionize oncology, with their structural diversity and unique bioactivity offering new hope for overcoming drug resistance and enhancing personalized cancer therapies. Pancreatic cancer remains a formidable challenge due to its aggressive nature and high metastatic potential [119]. Despite its relatively low prevalence, significant efforts have been made to develop novel therapeutic strategies, including cytotoxic agents and bioactive compounds. Marine biotechnology has contributed to anticancer research by providing novel bioactive compounds derived from marine invertebrates, seaweeds, fungi, and bacteria. Marine-origin biomaterials such as chitosan, fucoidan, and alginate have shown promise in advanced cancer therapies, with marine-derived nanoparticles demonstrating enhanced drug delivery and reduced cytotoxicity [120]. Marine natural products have been pivotal in targeting cancer stem cells and are

tissue injury. For example, marine macromolecule-cross-linked biocomposite scaffolds have demonstrated anti-inflammatory effects both in vitro and in vivo [115]. Fucoïdan, a sulfated polysaccharide derived from brown algae, is notable for its anti-inflammatory potential, making it a promising candidate for therapeutic applications [129]. Yapeng Lu et al. developed double-crosslinked gelatin hydrogels with improved antibacterial and anti-inflammatory properties for wound-healing applications. A gelatin-based Tsg-THA&Fe hydrogel was prepared by forming a THA-Fe³⁺ complex, which was subsequently cross-linked with tilapia skin gelatin via a Schiff base reaction. The gelation duration and rheological characteristics were modified by altering the intricate composition. The dynamic coordination of ophthalmic triol-Fe³⁺ and Schiff base links endowed the hydrogel with enhanced injectability, self-healing ability, and beneficial biocompatibility, biodegradability, adhesion, hemostatic, and antibacterial properties in vitro. In a rat skin trauma model, the Tsg-THA&Fe hydrogel significantly reduced microbial load, inhibited bacterial colonization, alleviated inflammation, and accelerated wound healing compared with the Comfeel® Plus Transparent dressing. Moreover, local application demonstrated no organ toxicity, suggesting its potential as a multi-functional wound dressing for improved healing outcomes [130].

3.5.7. Bioactivity and cell proliferation

Marine algae are rich in bioactive compounds, including proteins, carbohydrates, minerals, fatty acids, antioxidants, and pigments, which contribute to cell proliferation and bioactivity. These metabolites, influenced by biotic and abiotic factors, have been harnessed for nanotheranostic applications, particularly in the synthesis of nanoparticles for biomedical applications [126]. Hydroxyapatite, polycaprolactone, and gelatin scaffolds fabricated via 3D printing have demonstrated promising bioactivity and drug-delivery potential for the treatment of bone cancer [131]. Similarly, HA-collagen scaffolds incorporating antibiotics like ciprofloxacin and gentamicin have demonstrated enhanced cell adhesion and proliferation. Ti6Al4V titanium alloy coatings modified with biphasic calcium phosphate and graphene have shown enhanced corrosion resistance and improved viability of MG-63 cells [132]. In nano-dentistry, eggshell-derived nano-HAp composites have enhanced dental bioactivity and proliferation. Additionally, poly(lactic acid) blends with biopolymers have improved mechanical properties for medical applications, including wound healing and drug delivery. These advancements highlight the potential of bioactive polymers in regenerative medicine and biomedical applications [133]. Tayyeb Ghadimi et al. developed a collagen-blended sponge for accelerated wound-healing applications. The physicochemical and biological characterization of synthesized collagen (40 mg/ml) and SGE (1–3 mg/ml) scaffolds confirmed the presence of bioactive components in SGE. The existence of type I collagen ($\alpha 1$ and $\alpha 2$), effective SGE integration, substantial thermal stability, and elevated hydrophilicity with superior water absorption. Biological assessments revealed significant antioxidant and antibacterial properties, increased structural stability against degradation, and augmented cell proliferation without harmful effects. Among the formulations, Col/SGE with 3 mg/ml SGE demonstrated the superior antibacterial efficacy and cell viability. In rats, it hastened burn wound healing with improved re-epithelialization, dermal remodeling, decreased inflammation, fibroblast activity, and collagen deposition [76].

4. Recent developments in marine-based wound dressing systems

There are numerous biomaterials made from marine-inspired biopolymers, including scaffolds, hydrogels, and nanofibers, each with a specific biomedical application, as shown in Table 2. The natural origin, biocompatibility, and potential customization of these biomaterials across various therapeutic areas confer significant benefits. The diverse nature of polymers of marine origin enables the development of new

Table 2
Summary of different dressing materials based on biopolymers.

Dressing materials	Composition	Biomedical characteristics	References
Hydrogels	Chitosan, zinc nanoparticles, dopamine	Anti-oxidant, biocompatible, hemostasis, anti-bacterial activity, collagen deposition, reduced inflammation	[134]
Scaffolds	Gelatin, bacterial cellulose, PVA	Anti-bacterial activity, biodegradation, swellability, hydrophilicity, hemocompatibility, and cell proliferation	[135]
Nanofibers	Chitosan, silver nanoparticles, polyethylene oxide	Anti-bacterial activity, anti-oxidant activity, cytocompatibility	[136]
Microneedles	Hyaluronic acid, chitosan, and sodium alginate	Collagen deposition, Transforming growth factor- $\beta 1$, Cell viability, Proliferation accelerated wound healing.	[137]

materials tailored for a wide range of applications, including tissue engineering, drug delivery, and wound healing. Ongoing research into how these materials can be optimized and functionalized to improve therapeutic outcomes is ongoing.

4.1. Nanofibers

Electrospinning is a standard method for producing nanofibrous scaffolds from polymers derived from marine sources, which are being researched for future drug delivery and tissue engineering applications. These nanofibrous scaffolds provide a favorable environment for tissue healing and cell growth because they closely mimic the ECM [138]. The surface area-to-volume ratio of nanofibers is very high, which is a significant factor in increasing cell attachment and improving the quality of drug delivery systems. The effectiveness of nanofibrous scaffolds, especially those based on chitosan and alginate, in various wound-healing procedures is being scrutinized [139]. Jia et al. prepared nanofibers from chitosan and PEO for use as wound dressings and reported that they have no adhesive properties. These include the antibacterial effects and the high rate of gas and vapor exchange, which facilitate rapid wound healing, as observed in Fig. 6. They were shown to exhibit increased cell proliferation, superior antibacterial activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, and cytocompatibility. They reported faster wound healing within 10 days, and the engineered dressing has potential as a material for wound-healing applications [140]. Sun et al. have synthesized nanofiber hydrogels from fish scale, sodium alginate, and chitosan via in situ crosslinking. Copper sulfide nanoparticles were synthesized via a one-step technique. The results showed 49.96% and 51.32% antibacterial activities against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, respectively, and after 14 days, the nanofiber hydrogels exhibited 52.68% degradation and 87.56% voidage [141]. Shohreh et al. have produced electrospun nanofibers from PCL/chitosan laced with curcumin@chitosan to assess wound-healing efficacy, with a mean diameter of 214.9 nm, whereas Cur@CS electrospun had a mean diameter of 99.84 nm. The nanofiber had a stable structure, with a tensile stress of 7 MPa and an elongation of 35%. They also found that rapid wound healing of 96.25% and 98.5% occurred in MRSA-infected wounds, thus suggesting the possibility of improved wound healing [142].

4.2. Hydrogels

The marine-derived proteins and polysaccharides can easily form hydrogels, meaning 3D networks that absorb water, and are characterized by high bioactivity and biocompatibility. Their properties make

Fig. 6. The fabrication of nanofibrous dressing materials for wound healing applications, (A) Schematics of nanofiber fabrication and in vivo wound healing applications, (B) surface morphological with diameter distribution of nanofiber, (C) In vitro biological assays to determine anti-oxidant activities via DPPH, cell viability using L929 cell lines and surface morphology to determine the cell adherence via SEM, and (D) Digital photographs of wound healing after different time interval and H&E staining assay to evaluate the wound healing [140], Copyright (2024) with permission from Elsevier.

them the best choice for drug delivery and tissue engineering. The mechanical properties of hydrogels can be optimized by varying the biopolymer concentration and the cross-linking method [143]. Furthermore, self-healing hydrogels are being developed to enhance durability and stability in challenging environments. Incorporating nanoparticles into hydrogels further improves their properties, expanding their potential for advanced biomedical applications [144]. Wei et al. have developed a flexible epidermal sensor using Ag@polydopamine and chitosan hydrogel to monitor wound healing. They have optimized the hydrogel sensor for rapid recovery and structural durability, as shown in Fig. 7. It exhibited self-healing, tissue adhesion, and antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, and this sensor-based hydrogel facilitates accelerated wound healing by providing multifunctional health monitoring and wound care [145]. Farhana et al. have developed chitosan-PVA hydrogels containing marine collagen peptides as a wound dressing. They have prepared various formulations, such as PVA:chitosan: CP in a 5:1:1 ratio, with water absorption rates of 80 per cent, 900 per cent, and 40 per cent, respectively. The resulting hydrogels were structurally stable, with a compressive modulus of approximately 40 kPa, and demonstrated improved hemostatic behavior and antimicrobial effects [84]. Park et al. have reported the development of hydrogels via a Schiff base reaction from fish gelatin and oxidized hyaluronate for the treatment of diabetic wounds. Biological evolution indicates that these hydrogels are cytocompatible and reduce pro-inflammatory cytokine expression, including IL-1 β , PGE2, TNF- α , and NO, in lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-stimulated RAW 264.7

macrophages. The in vivo assays show collagen deposition and protein expression, including CD206, Arg1, and CD31, in the diabetic mouse model, and the developed hydrogels could be a potential wound dressing for diabetic wound-healing applications [146].

4.3. Scaffolds

Marine-derived biopolymers are increasingly utilized to fabricate scaffolds for tissue engineering, providing structural support and facilitating tissue regeneration. These scaffolds can be designed with varying porosity and fiber structures tailored to specific applications and biopolymer properties [147]. Marine collagen scaffolds have shown promise in bone tissue engineering, while chitosan and alginate-based scaffolds are being investigated for cartilage and other tissue applications. The addition of bioactive molecules or cells enhances the regenerative capabilities of these scaffolds. Additionally, cuttlefish bone is being studied as a sustainable source for bone repair and related applications [148]. Chen et al. have developed polysaccharide-based hydrogels with microenvironment stimuli for the treatment of diabetic foot ulcers by incorporating berberine, as shown in Fig. 8. They have observed that the fabricated hydrogel accelerates wound healing within 14 days. It also exhibited other biological activities, including antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant effects, to provide a desirable microenvironment for rapid wound repair [149]. Qi Fang et al. synthesized chitosan-gelatin scaffolds infused with antibiotics for the treatment of wounds infected by seawater exposure. Their results

Fig. 7. The synthesis of sensor-based hydrogels for wound healing monitoring and wound care, (A) illustration of synthesis of chitosan functionalization and silver@polydopamine nanoparticles and application for wound healing and care, (B) structural analysis by FTIR, XPS, RAMAN and XRD with TEM morphology and surface morphology of the hydrogel via SEM, (C) Digital photographs of wound healing after different time, graphical of wound closure and histopathological assay after 7 days, and (D) in vitro biological assays by hemocompatibility, optical density, cell morphology using L929 cell line, UV-analysis, DPPH assay, photothermal conversion and digital photographs of anti-bacterial against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* bacterial strains [145], Copyright (2024) with permission from Nature Publisher.

showed that CS/GEL/GMs-CIP possessed significant antibacterial properties against *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, and *E. coli*. The seawater-immersion animal wound-infection model was used to assess wound healing in vivo. The reconstructed composite scaffolds, enhancing the collagen deposition, reepithelialization, and wound healing, were accelerated. The deeper examination of the wound tissue showed that the anti-inflammatory factor (TGF- β 1) was expressed more. However, increased expression of pro-inflammatory factors (TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-1 β) and decreased serum endotoxin levels were observed, which will support accelerated wound healing [150]. Pathum et al. have synthesized electrospun porous bilayer nanofibers from fish collagen/PCL and cross-linked chitoooligosaccharides to produce bioactive scaffolds for deep wound healing. These findings indicate that the cross-linked nanofiber mats did not change significantly in either their fibrous morphology or their interconnected porous structure. The growth in fiber diameter is 388.33 ± 107.35 nm, 414.45 ± 129.91 nm, and 480.82 ± 115.40 nm with FCP 1:9, FCP 5:5, and FCP 9:1, respectively. The nanofibers had an increasing surface area, which may enhance wound healing by improving cellular function. It means that an increase in collagen content resulted in an increase in cross-linking efficiency at the fiber contacting surface and inside the fiber [151].

4.4. Microneedles

Microneedles have emerged as a promising approach for wound healing due to their ability to penetrate the stratum corneum, facilitating localized drug delivery with minimal invasiveness. A biomimetic MN patch (HepMi-PCL), inspired by corals, utilizes 3D printing technology to create a porous structure that enables exudate absorption and responsive drug release, thereby significantly enhancing wound healing in infected wounds [152]. Marine polysaccharides, such as alginate, fucoidan, and chitosan, are widely used in MN-based delivery systems to overcome the limitations of the skin barrier in pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications [153]. Bioinspired MNs, integrating anti-oxidant strategies from blueberries and wet adhesive mechanisms from cling-fish, demonstrate strong adhesion in moist environments and sustained drug release, proving effective in ocular wound healing models. Additionally, a multifunctional MN array patch incorporating chitosan (CS), fucoidan (FD), and traditional Chinese medicine kangfuxin accelerates full-thickness wound healing by promoting collagen deposition and anti-bacterial activity [154]. Polymeric MNs, enhanced with nano-materials, offer on-demand drug release, mechanical strength, and biocompatibility, positioning them as a transformative solution for wound management [155]. Junjie Chi et al. have developed

Fig. 8. The fabrication of hydrogel scaffolds with microenvironment stimuli for wound healing. (A) Schematic of hydrogel scaffold development and application, (B) digital photographs of anti-bacterial activities against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, (C) Strach analysis to determine the potential of hydrogels for wound healing applications and (D) Digital photographs of the wound healing after different days [149], Copyright (2024) with permission from Nature Publishers.

microneedle patches from chitosan with enhanced antibacterial and angiogenic properties for accelerated wound-healing applications, as shown in Fig. 9. They have reported that the newly developed microneedles sustain drug release and adhere to the skin, making them potential dressing materials for wound-healing applications [156]. Ayesha et al. have reported the fabrication of microneedle patches from pullulan incorporating fucoidan@chitosan nanoparticles, with sustained drug release for accelerated wound healing. Moxifloxacin (MOX)-loaded nanoparticles require the use of chitosan and fucoidan. The surface potential is $45.1 \text{ mV} \pm 3.9 \text{ mV}$, the diameter is $258.0 \text{ nm} \pm 10.86 \text{ nm}$, and the polydispersity index is 0.19 ± 0.06 . Thrombin, lidocaine, moxifloxacin nanoparticles, and a 30% (w/w) pullulan-based microneedle patch are then incorporated. The microneedle patches comprise conical, homogeneous microneedles measuring 725, 500, and 350 mm in length. It demonstrates adequate penetration strength on the skin and favorable biocompatibility. It is readily absorbed through the skin ($55 \pm 5 \text{ min}$), with the release of TH and LH occurring swiftly, whereas MOX release is sustained for 24 h. Microneedles can repair wounds on murine skin within 7 days, facilitating collagen deposition and enhancing recovery. This study develops a smart functional microneedle technology with rapid hemostasis and persistent antibacterial properties using chitosan and pullulan polysaccharides [157].

5. Critical comparative analysis

A comprehensive comparison of marine- and non-marine-derived biopolymers is necessary to understand how they work, their limitations, and their biological applications. Marine-derived biopolymers, such as collagen, chitosan, alginate, fucoidan, and gelatin sourced from

fish, crustaceans, and algae, have attracted significant attention due to their remarkable biocompatibility, biodegradability, and structural similarity to native ECM components [91]. These materials often exhibit intrinsic bioactivities, including antibacterial, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory properties. These are particularly advantageous for wound healing, tissue regeneration, and drug delivery systems. Conversely, non-marine-derived biopolymers, including cellulose, hyaluronic acid, silk fibroin, mammalian collagen, and synthetic biodegradable polymers, possess a more extensive history of clinical application and advantage from standardized processing, established extraction methods, and regulatory familiarity. However, concerns over zoonotic disease transmission, religious prohibitions, and ethical issues related to animal sources may limit their extensive implementation [158]. Marine-derived biopolymers exhibit increased hydrophilicity, enhanced swelling, and moderate gelation properties. Under physiological conditions, making them especially suitable for soft-tissue engineering and wound treatment. Marine collagen often exhibits lower denaturation temperatures compared to mammalian collagen. It enhances processability but may compromise thermal and mechanical integrity. Conversely, non-marine biopolymers such as silk fibroin and cellulose exhibit greater mechanical strength and thermal stability, making them more suitable for load-bearing tissues and long-term implantable devices. This disparity highlights a crucial trade-off between bioactivity and mechanical strength. It often necessitates composite or hybrid systems to integrate these qualities for specific therapeutic goals [159]. Biological performance further differentiates marine biopolymer systems from their non-marine counterparts. Materials derived from marine sources frequently enhance cell adhesion, proliferation, and angiogenesis. These arise from the existence of

Fig. 9. The microneedle array for wound healing applications, (A) Schematics of microneedle patch fabrication from the marine source for wound and application for wound, (B) Digital photograph and SEM morphology of the microneedle patches and (C) Schematic illustration of different wound healing phases, digital photographs of the wound healing after different days and histopathology using microneedle patches [156], Copyright (2020) with permission from Elsevier.

bioactive peptides and sulfated polysaccharides. Their inherent antibacterial and antioxidant properties reduce the risk of infection and oxidative harm. These are particularly beneficial in the treatment of chronic and burn wounds [160]. Conversely, non-marine biopolymers generally exhibit enhanced cytocompatibility and uniform degradation. Nonetheless, they often lack intrinsic bioactivity and require functionalization with growth factors, peptides, or drugs to achieve comparable therapeutic outcomes. This requirement increases system complexity and cost while enabling improved regulation of biological signaling. Despite their advantages, marine-derived biopolymers face challenges including batch-to-batch variability, seasonal availability of raw materials, and limited large-scale clinical validation [19]. Moreover, their rapid degradation and reduced mechanical integrity may restrict their use in situations necessitating prolonged structural support. Non-aquatic biopolymers are more standardized and physically resilient. These may provoke immunogenic responses due to their origin and processing methods, and may exhibit slower degradation rates that do not align

with tissue regeneration rates. Thus, the choice of materials must be guided by criteria relevant to the application, encompassing degradation kinetics, mechanical properties, biological effectiveness, and regulatory considerations [161]. Consequently, marine-derived biopolymers are particularly suitable for applications requiring enhanced bioactivity, rapid tissue integration, and infection control. These encompass wound healing, skin regeneration, and targeted drug delivery. In contrast, non-marine-derived biopolymers are beneficial for applications requiring structural integrity and integration into bone tissue engineering, sutures, and long-term implants, where mechanical integrity and regulatory compliance are paramount. A thorough comparative examination of various material classes facilitates the selection or incorporation of certain biopolymer systems to enhance treatment efficacy and mitigate limitations [158].

6. Regulatory approaches to marine-based biopolymers

Wound healing biopolymers derived from marine sources need to be tested for safety, efficacy, and biocompatibility before clinical applications. Both the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and European Medicines Agency (EMA) require extensive preclinical and clinical trials to ensure that biopolymers comply with biomedicine. Marine-derived polymers include alginate, chitosan, and collagen; therefore, extra care is taken in their extraction, purification, and assessment of allergenicity to prevent an immunological response [162]. These materials must also meet GMP standards for uniformity, sterility, and traceability. The regulatory framework examines marine resource harvesting and its environmental and sustainability impacts, integrating ecological preservation into biomedical innovation. The acceptance process for biopolymers used in wound care derived from the sea entails consideration of ethical and environmental concerns, as well as their medical benefits for hemostasis, cell growth, and tissue regeneration [163].

6.1. Sustainable regulatory

There are sustainable regulatory issues to the use of marine-based biopolymers in wound healing. It is primarily due to the need to balance safety compliance, ethical sourcing, and environmental preservation with biological innovation. Collagen, chitosan, alginates, and carrageenan are marine-based polymers sourced from renewable resources of the marine environment and offer biodegradable, biocompatible alternatives to synthetic polymers. However, they involve excessive extraction, raising ecological concerns, including overfishing of aquatic organisms and possible disruption of marine environments [164]. Regulatory frameworks should therefore ensure traceability, homogeneity of raw materials, and sustainable harvesting processes to

reduce environmental impact. Another aspect to note is that the physical and chemical properties of marine biopolymers vary from batch to batch. Biological applications require a careful characterization, toxicological evaluation, and compliance with international standards, such as ISO 10993. The determination of clear guidelines on how to obtain, handle, and use these materials in a therapeutic setting. Ensuring the long-term ecological sustainability of wound-healing solutions derived from marine biopolymers should be as important as patient safety and product efficacy [165].

6.2. Harvesting biopolymers from marine resources

There are significant scientific and regulatory issues regarding the extraction of biopolymers from marine resources, especially regarding their future use in wound dressings. The marine-derived biopolymers (collagen, carrageenan, chitosan, alginate, and fucoidan) are synthesized by a multitude of species. These include the sea sponges, algae, and crustaceans, which have excellent biocompatibility, biodegradability, and bioactivity. Extraction and processing must follow strict environmental and regulatory standards to enable the sustainable use of resources and ensure product safety [166]. Since the marine ecosystem's balance may be disrupted by excessive exploitation of aquatic organisms, there is an urgent need to adopt controlled aquaculture practices and eco-friendly harvesting methods. FDA and EMA promote standardized purification, toxicity testing, and clinical testing to ensure batch-to-batch consistency and reduce immunogenicity and contamination. Therefore, biopolymers derived from the seas have considerable potential for developing superior biomaterials for wound healing. The combination of sustainable harvesting methods with strict regulatory compliance and quality assurance is significant for their use as a treatment method [167]. The regulatory approaches for marine-derived

Fig. 10. The regulatory approaches for marine-derived biopolymers.

biopolymers have been illustrated in Fig. 10.

6.3. Medical device

The use of marine biopolymers in wound healing is considered medical equipment and must undergo rigorous safety and effectiveness evaluations. It is a thorough set of bench tests, which is paramount to the regulatory inspection process. It includes sterility tests to verify the absence of toxic pollutants. Leachable analysis determines potentially harmful substances produced during use, and cytotoxicity studies assess biocompatibility with human cells [168]. The structural feasibility of the biopolymer during physiological conditions should also be checked by mechanical testing. During these tests, the relevant ISO standards, such as the ISO 10993 on biocompatibility and ISO 11135 on sterilization validation, are usually followed. In addition, clinical performance data is essential for supporting the drug's therapeutic effects. These are its capabilities to achieve optimal wound healing, prevent infection, and enhance tissue regeneration [168,169].

6.4. Products with combined therapy

Marine-based biopolymers are engineered to contain bioactive molecules for wound-healing applications, thereby complicating their regulation. These composite systems may require additional pharmacological and toxicological testing to ensure their safety, efficacy, and biocompatibility under these conditions [164]. Introduction of therapeutic drugs introduces physiologically active substances that can provoke local or systemic biological reactions. These require careful evaluation in accordance with the biological or pharmacological regulatory measures. The developers must therefore adhere to detailed regulatory standards. These include factors related to controlled release, dose optimization, and potential adverse effects, to ensure it meets the high standards of clinical translation and marketing [170].

6.5. Source transparency and characterization

Regulatory bodies require strict, standardized characterization procedures for biological materials. It guarantees consistency, safety, and effectiveness within batches, especially in wound therapy. It includes detailed characterization of the molecular mass distributions, levels of impurities, and endotoxins of biopolymers of marine derivation. It can significantly affect immunogenic responses and biological functions. However, the natural variability of raw biomaterials and seasonal changes in their composition also pose unique challenges in meeting these requirements [171]. There are additional hurdles, such as developing reproducible, scalable production processes that comply with good manufacturing practices (GMP) requirements for regulatory approval. It leads to the conclusion that the use of marine-based biomaterials for therapeutic wound healing requires complex diagnostic methods, and strict quality control measures should be implemented in accordance with regulatory requirements [171].

7. Clinical translational roadmap of marine biopolymers

The translational roadmap for marine biopolymers provides a step-wise approach to advancing fundamental research toward therapeutic and industrial applications. The first step in this process is the extraction and characterization of marine biopolymers, such as chitosan, alginate, carrageenan, and fucoidan. It focuses on their inherent bioactivities, including immunomodulatory, biocompatible, biodegradable, and antimicrobial properties [164]. It is followed by optimizing these materials through chemical modification, crosslinking, or nanostructuring to enhance their mechanical strength and functional performance. Pre-clinical assessment of their biological safety, efficacy, and properties during physiological conditions is then confirmed [172]. Finally, to achieve successful clinical translation, compliance with regulatory

requirements, mass production, and integration into superior biomedical devices or formulations are crucial. This clinical roadmap highlights the need to incorporate interdisciplinary collaboration to maximize the therapeutic potential of marine biopolymers in regenerative medicine and other health-related fields [173]. The clinical roadmap for developing marine-based biopolymers into wound-healing dressings is illustrated in Fig. 11.

7.1. Early clinical feasibility trials

The use of adaptive methods is particularly relevant to wound-healing solutions, where timely therapeutic intervention is necessary. The attractive wound care product can be made of marine polymers because it can provide hemostasis, antibacterial properties, and tissue regeneration. Adaptive trials enable investigators to promptly assess the benefits of therapy and adjust study parameters as clinical responses change. When a marine hydrogel comprising polymers improves wound healing or reduces infection, interim testing can inform subsequent phases of the trial [173]. Adaptive trial designs offer the benefit of evaluating innovative wound-healing treatments ethically and cost-effectively by reducing exposure to non-promising treatments and focusing on promising therapies. The possibility of standardizing biopolymers derived from the sea is also an essential obstacle to their use in treatment. The different source organisms, extraction methods, and purification protocols yield materials with varying molecular weights, degrees of acetylation, and impurity profiles, which affect therapeutic activity and safety [174]. Clinical trials should be appropriately characterized and meet regulatory standards early to ensure stability and reproducibility. Bioengineering, materials science, and clinical research are required to enhance manufacturing through GMP while maintaining bioactivity. Therefore, to improve material preparation and standardization processes for clinical deployment, early-phase clinical trials assess safety and feasibility [175].

7.2. Adaptive trial designs

Adaptive trial designs are dynamic and successful in clinical assessment, particularly in the development of wound-healing therapies using marine polymers. In contrast to the predetermined designs applied in the past, in adaptive trials, real-time amendments can be made based on provisional findings. It will help the researcher to make informed choices regarding dose changes, recalibration of sample sizes, or even termination of studies before completion due to efficacy or futility. Adaptability reduces the overall number of patients required and, at the same time, improves the process of detecting indicators of safety and effectiveness [175]. Biopolymers derived from marine sources, such as fucoidan, alginate, and chitosan, are referred to in this context. Adaptive designs can assist in early-phase clinical trials by prioritizing patient safety and allocating resources in the most timely and effective manner possible. Especially given that various biomaterials exhibit unique bioactivity and biocompatibility. The integration of adaptive methods is particularly relevant in wound-healing products, where timely therapeutic intervention is required [172]. The promising properties in marine polymers are their hemostatic, bacterial, and tissue regeneration properties that make them an attractive wound care choice. Adaptive trials enable researchers to promptly assess the benefits of therapy and adjust study conditions in response to changes in clinical response. If a hydrogel based on marine polymers contributes to wound closure or reduces infection, interim assessments are likely to guide future trials. Adaptive trial designs aid the ethical and efficient exploration of novel wound-healing remedies, minimize exposure to ineffective treatments, and focus on promising candidate treatments [176].

7.3. Public-private partnerships

Public-private partnerships (PPPs) are instrumental in advancing the

Fig. 11. The clinical road map of the marine-based biopolymers to develop dressing materials for wound healing applications.

translational potential of marine-derived polymers for wound-healing applications. It bridges regulatory compliance, industrial progress, and scholarly research. Marine biopolymers such as chitosan, alginate, agarose, and fucoidan have demonstrated significant bioactivity in preclinical studies, with particular applications in enhancing cell proliferation, blood clotting, and antibacterial properties [177]. Careful analyses of Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) and Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP) are also essential for transitioning a lab-scale development to a clinically viable product. At academic institutions, PPPs support basic research on the physical, chemical, and biological properties and actions of these polymers. The private sector, however, provides vital funds, resources, and expertise in the design of clinical trials, the regulatory process, and the scalability of manufacturing [178]. Such partnerships enhance innovation and ensure bioactivity and safety of marine polymer-based wound dressings even during large-scale production. Some hurdles can impede regulatory approval and the scaling of marine-derived wound-healing therapies. Potential obstacles include batch-to-batch variation, storage stability, and the need for a standardized testing protocol. PPPs lessen these difficulties by providing access to the most advanced facilities, such as ISO-certified production lines and bioreactors, which are required to develop high-quality polymers under GMP regulations. More so, in cases where scientific and business interests are commensurate, translational projects are sustained as both economically feasible and scientifically sound [179]. The partnerships also facilitate easier regulatory compliance, enabling early interaction with agencies such as the FDA or EMA to accelerate product approval. PPPs will accelerate the development of marine polymer-based research into clinically approved wound-healing medicines, benefiting the healthcare sector and encouraging eco-friendly biomedical innovation [180].

7.4. Harmonized reporting standards

It requires standardized reporting in academic journals to enable large-scale meta-analyses of marine biopolymers as medical adjuvants for wound healing. The sources, recovery procedures, and

physicochemical characterization of such biopolymers are currently described in various ways by scientists. It makes it difficult to relate and integrate the results of numerous studies. Harvesting variations, purification methods, or species can lead to significant changes in polymer production and bioactivity [181]. These factors could affect the efficacy of the polymers as wound-healing agents. It would improve transparency and reproducibility by developing standardized approaches and reporting specifications. The information may include a detailed description of the biopolymer's origin, the extraction method, molecular weight, purity, chemical composition, and biological examination. It will not just enhance the accuracy of individual investigations, but also provide a sound basis for data aggregation via meta-analysis [182]. Standardization would allow quantitative meta-analyses with a variety of studies and determine the effectiveness of treatments using various types and formulations of polymers. This harmonization is necessary because of the diverse biological activities of marine biopolymers and their sensitivity to external and processing forces. Consistent reporting would improve the clinical adoption of such biomaterials and facilitate the development of regulatory frameworks and translational pathways. The standardized protocols will enable researchers to conduct extensive comparisons and optimize marine polymers for wound healing, thereby enhancing trial rigor and accelerating innovation [183].

7.5. Digital biomaterials databases

Digital databases of biomaterials help centralize data from raw material extraction through clinical trial outcomes, transforming decision-making for marine-derived polymers. These systems combine physicochemical attributes, biocompatibility tests, degradation rate, and toxicity data of numerous sources in the ocean, including chitosan, algin, and collagen. Systematic, organized datasets can enable researchers and physicians to test the compatibility of materials for wound healing [184]. It minimizes biomaterial development trial-and-error and encourages the development of custom wound-healing solutions with greater therapeutic value and improved patient outcomes. In addition, a deeper understanding of material-host interactions is gained through

comparisons between the biological performance of marine polymers and the conditions of their origin and processing. Behavioral properties *in vivo*, such as angiogenesis, antimicrobial activity, and tissue regeneration, are linked to molecular weight, degree of deacetylation (in chitosan), and crosslinking density [185]. This scientific knowledge helps determine the best feedstocks for different types of wounds, such as burns, diabetic, and chronic wounds. The ultimate factor in improving the application of marine biopolymers in wound therapy and personalized medicine is the development of digital banks of biomaterials [23].

8. Current challenges and future recommendations

Marine-based biopolymers need to be tested for solubility, mechanical properties, extraction variability, scalability, and biocompatibility for clinical use in treating chronic wounds. The source and level of deacetylation, and the molecular weight of marine-based polymers such as chitosan, alginate, and collagen, affect the solubility of the biopolymers and their physicochemical and biological characteristics. The limited aqueous solubility inhibits their processability and homogeneous dispersion in hydrogel or scaffold formulations, thereby reducing therapeutic efficacy [186]. The lack of tensile strength and flexibility in most marine biopolymers makes them insufficient to withstand physiological loads under dynamic wound conditions. It may require chemical modification or amalgamation with synthetic polymers to achieve mechanical stability without loss of biodegradability or bioactivity. Additional challenges in their clinical application include scalability and unpredictable extraction. The physicochemical properties of marine biopolymers depend on species, location, and extraction method, resulting in batch-to-batch variation and inconsistent reproducibility [187]. Inequalities of this kind can preclude large-scale manufacturing and prevent the government from imposing sanctions. Additional limitations that affect scalability include the limited supply of high-purity marine raw materials and the high costs associated with environmentally sensitive extraction and purification methods. In biocompatibility-sensitive conditions, a thorough evaluation is essential, as residual pollutants, toxins, and unreacted crosslinkers can trigger an inflammatory or immune response. The biodegradability and cytocompatibility of marine biopolymers are well documented; however, limited information exists regarding the impact of their breakdown products on the tissues of chronic wounds. Material chemistry, process optimization, and biological evaluation should therefore be necessary to overcome these enormous challenges and improve the efficacy of marine-derived biopolymers for chronic wound healing [188]. Marine biomaterial development has improved, but more research is needed in the following areas to harness their potential. It is necessary to ensure the homogeneity and reproducibility of marine-based biopolymers by standardizing extraction and processing methods. It would encourage their continued use in biomedical fields by providing reliable materials for diverse applications. Biological studies are needed to determine the safety and efficacy of these biomaterials for real-life applications. These materials should be examined as biological characteristics in the living organisms over time, such as biodegradability, tissue contact, and immunological response [19,189]. Moreover, mechanistic insights into the effects of marine-derived biomaterials on cells and tissues remain underdeveloped, hindering the design of these materials for wound healing. The study of functional groups and surface modification will also allow biomaterials to suit specific medicinal needs. Scalable, cost-effective production processes are needed to meet the increasing demand for marine-based biomaterials as wound dressings in clinical practice [23]. It entails developing new extraction processes and bioprocessing technologies to streamline the process and reduce costs. The discovery of the widespread biodiversity of marine organisms could lead to the development of novel biopolymers with distinct properties and functions. There is a need to improve coordination among marine biologists, chemists, and biomedical engineers to develop new dressing

materials with faster functions. Lastly, regulatory and safety and compliance issues are also vital in the effective clinical implementation of these biomaterials. Researchers, industry players and regulatory bodies will play a central role in solving such issues and developing marine-inspired dressing materials to be used in biological and clinical use aspects of wound healing [190].

Marine biopolymers are better candidates for new wound-healing applications in fast-evolving 3D and 4D bioprinting due to their unique physicochemical properties. Their biocompatibility, biodegradability, and ability to mimic the extracellular matrix facilitate the development of customized scaffolds that enhance cell adhesion, proliferation, and tissue regeneration. The 3D bioprinting of these polymers enables precise spatial deposition to form patient-specific wound dressings with controlled porosity, mechanical strength, and drug-loading capacity [191]. The bioprinting of 4D structures enables them to respond to environmental factors such as pH, temperature, and humidity. It allows the delivery of drugs on demand or structural alteration to conform to the shape of wounds. Research in the future ought to focus on enhancing the mechanical and bioactivity of inks produced from marine biopolymers, the addition of growth factors or antibacterial compounds, and the development of scalable syntheses to make them clinically relevant. Additionally, interdisciplinary collaboration among physicians, biomedical engineers, and materials scientists should be encouraged to improve these systems for the management of complex and chronic wounds in real healthcare settings [192].

9. Conclusions

Marine-derived biopolymers are promising biomaterials for wound healing and have demonstrated potential in wound dressings due to their biocompatibility, biodegradability, and inherent bioactivity. Marine biopolymers are dynamic molecules with distinct biochemical compositions that may be used in novel wound-healing strategies. The lack of standardized characterizations impedes regulatory approval and the reproducibility of cross-study results. The lack of standardization complicates the scalability of the issue across sectors, hindering scientific validation. The lack of robust clinical trial evidence on the long-term safety, efficacy, and effects of marine biopolymers in humans is a significant limitation. Despite its potential, the majority of current evidence is preclinical or derived from small experimental cohorts, rendering it inadequate for the formulation of effective therapeutic guidelines. Extensive, regulated clinical trials can enhance healthcare implementation and regulatory applications. The agreement will specify the ideal application concepts and delineate the therapeutic effects of marine biopolymers. It encompasses dosage formulations and patient responses, which influence evidence-based treatment. These issues necessitate a multidisciplinary approach involving physicians, researchers, industry stakeholders, and regulatory agencies. Researchers expedited wound-healing research to better understand intrinsic healing processes by designing single-layer dressing materials for all wound types, a challenge due to inadequate wound healing and varying patient sensitivities. Wound healing is a multistage process, despite the simplicity of dressing development. Research in medical technologies and wound healing indicates that wound dressings may be capable of promptly assessing wound healing, exhibiting multifunctional properties, and responding to alterations in the wound environment, thereby enabling them to deliver customized wound care. Their benefits, multifunctional dressing materials promote wound healing. Henceforth, research groups must concentrate on medical examinations to authenticate and enhance study outcomes. The safety, efficacy, and biological impacts of several treatment combinations require investigation. As innovative methods lose therapeutic utility, production costs continue to escalate. Enhanced wound care procedures necessitate improved production and formulation of safe and effective dressing materials. Marine-derived polymeric materials provide sustainable, biocompatible alternatives to synthetic polymers, thereby advancing the field of

biomaterials science. Marine-derived polymers are optimal for biomedical engineering applications owing to their distinctive physical, chemical, and biological characteristics. Marine resources are abundant and renewable, rendering them suitable for extensive production and utilities. Ultimately, marine biopolymers hold significant therapeutic potential, paving the way for the development of bioactive dressings for wound healing applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Muhammad Umar Aslam Khan: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Saiqa Yousaf:** Funding acquisition, Methodology, Resources, Software, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Abdalla Abdal-Hay:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Resources, Software, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Mohd Faizal Bin Abdullah:** Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Sahar Madani:** Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Muhammad Shahzad Zafar:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Project administration, Validation. **Goran M. Stojanović:** Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Lobat Tayebi:** Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Software, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

All the authors have declared no conflict of interest.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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